

1 C308F

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 C308F

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 C308F

● C
● F

■ shallow
■ intermediate
■ deep
■ NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 C308F

C
F

shallow
intermediate
deep
NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12